

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D4.3

Report on impact of integrated access standards tested for open user access

WP4 – Community-driven cross-infrastructure joint research - Bioscience

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Executive Summary

The mission of this WP is to support advanced user projects in need of a diverse set of technologies and services thereby enabling cutting-edge research. WP4 has focused on offering shared life science services by establishing common service pipelines between multiple ESFRI Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS RI). Pipelines between service providers were refined in several rounds, starting with VIP projects, then opening up the services to the general scientific community via two Open Calls.

This deliverable demonstrates the impact that the establishment of common service pipelines between multiple LS RIs has generated - for the user, for the RI, and for the scientific community. The Open Calls have given broad visibility to the RIs and have attracted genuinely new user groups to RI services and have thereby also increased the user-base of the individual RI. The Open Calls have enabled cross-cutting interdisciplinary projects, which allow the users to advance in their research and to open new avenues in science. The highly innovative and exploratory nature of the Open Call applications make them a high risk-high reward operation. As exploring new technologies with uncertain outcomes is not likely funded in individual research grants, open access programmes and the intense support from LS RI hubs for cross-RI access become critical. Further, the Open Calls have exposed that transnational access to research data from human participants is challenging and a significant bottleneck. Due to the Coronavirus pandemic at present 75% of 2nd Open Call projects got interrupted and have not been able to complete their visits yet.

To secure a leading role for Europe in life science research and to ensure the technological support needed for cutting-edge scientific projects, it is indispensable to develop mechanisms that will maintain access to these service pipelines also beyond CORBEL. To this end, the LS RIs maintain opportunities for cross-RI access via bilateral collaboration agreements and joint calls and work closely together in the cluster to explore opportunities for future calls across RIs with funders and deepen the alignment to include the full project life cycle including FAIR data and analysis via EOSC.

Project objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) Start to establish an infrastructure platform that integrates services for life science and support scientific research projects that require joint services between different ESFRI LS RIs
- b) Start to build cross-ESFRI LS infrastructure pipelines according to specific use case objectives
- c) Start to build the framework for transnational open user access for the sustainable use of the shared services

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

To establish research and service pipelines between RIs, joint service and access modalities were created allowing access to technologies and services offered by 10 of the LS RIs (BBMRI-ERIC, EATRIS-ERIC, ECRIN-ERIC, ELIXIR, EMBRC-ERIC, EU-OS ERIC, EuBI ERIC, INFRAFRONTIER, Instruct-ERIC, and ISBE). Together, cutting-edge services were made available at more than 20 service providers.

This allowed the realization of community-driven cross-infrastructure research projects at first via direct personal contact, and subsequently via Open Calls for project proposals. This user-led approach defines and develops the services required for cutting-edge European research projects, enables the life science RIs to support users throughout the execution of a scientific project and supports a new model for biological research, visibly reducing redundancy. Experimental project pipelines across the RIs were established for integrative approaches and gap-free transition from one technology to the next. Project requirements, testing and feedback drove the development of these shared services. Maintaining a close communication with all service providers and Open Call users has been a crucial factor for the success of the Open Calls. To facilitate interaction among service providers and between service providers and users, to exchange best practices for and to collect feedback on service provision, two face-to-face meetings were organised. Feedback on the overall experience of the service provision including the impact on the research of the users was collected in a survey entitled “CORBEL Final User Survey” (see Appendix). Similarly, the service providers were questioned on their experience in the “CORBEL Final Service Provider Survey” (see Appendix). The analysis on the impact of integrated access standards tested for open user access presented below is largely based on the results of these two surveys.

Description of Work

1. Impact of integrated access standards on CORBEL Open Call Users

Awareness of existing services and technology offers has been a challenge for LS RIs. The CORBEL Open Call led to an increased visibility of the participating RIs in the scientific user community. 68% of the accepted users were not aware of RIs and their service offer prior to the CORBEL Open Call (CORBEL Final User Survey, Q.U1). **96% of users have an interest in using the service and technology offers of RIs also in the future**, either individually at a single RI (46%) or collectively across multiple RIs (50%) (Q.U18) and highly valued the quality of service provided by individual service providers (26% good, 58% very good) (Q.U2). This clearly demonstrates the capacity of RIs to address the need for advanced services and technologies in the life science community. As life science projects are becoming increasingly complex and interdisciplinary, the goal of the CORBEL Open Calls was to realize excellent support for scientific projects across multiple RIs. In accordance, the users rate added value of the interconnection between RIs established in the CORBEL framework predominantly either good (41%) or very good (45%) (Q.U4). To establish successful service pipelines a centralized project management support throughout the entire project was introduced. Communication and collaboration between individual service providers along the project pipeline and the effectiveness of the centralized support were highly appreciated by the users. Communication was rated good by 50% and very good by 27% (Q.U5). The effectiveness of the centralized project support achieved the rating very good from 41% and very good from 50% of the users (Q.U3). One user summarized ‘Fantastic service providers and resources - the only challenge was perhaps bridging the RIs, getting everyone to meet and interact is difficult simply because of juggling so many schedules.’ underscoring the importance of a coordinated project support, facilitating the interaction, for the success of this highly interdisciplinary endeavor.

1.1 CORBEL Open Call User benefits - Impact on research

The scientific impact of the CORBEL projects on the research focus of the CORBEL users was also rated predominantly high (64% very good, 14% good) (Q.U6). Benefits offered that contribute to the added value include access to otherwise unavailable technologies and highly skilled technical

expertise, such as instrument usage (36% high benefit, 36% very high benefit) (Q.U11), data and analysis tools (14% high benefit, 27% very high benefit) (Q.U12), user support (36% high benefit, 41% very high benefit) (Q.U13), and training (27% high benefit, 32% very high benefit) (Q.U14). Testimonials of CORBEL Open Call users second the positive response of the survey, as Jenny Ostrop (EU-OS ERIC/EuBI ERIC), an expert on gut organelles emphasized 'I would definitely recommend other researchers to apply for access to the European research infrastructures. Their offer means a great chance to use instruments that you would normally not have access to and to benefit from their expertise.' (1). Alexey Koval (EU-OS ERIC/Instruct-ERIC) stated 'I had a unique and exciting opportunity to deepen my knowledge in large-scale hit identification. Both through communication and hands-on experience, I learned the details of the high-throughput screening setup, beginning from assay transfer and adaptation and finishing with the statistical methods of quality control and large dataset treatment. Our project will strongly benefit from the results obtained [...] at the requested CORBEL facilities.' (1). One user underlined 'The CORBEL grant provided me access [to] some very important technologies that I simply had no access to' and adds in regards to using cutting-edge technologies and receiving training from experts and that accessing RIs via the Open Call is an also 'excellent opportunity for students' (Q.U10). Access to technologies and the quality of data also convinced Maria Paola Martelli as she states 'CORBEL is allowing us access to technologies not available in our lab and to scale-up screening of large compound libraries. This is a big step forward needed for our project'(1). Johan Decelle (EuBI ERIC/EMBRC-ERIC) underlined 'learning about these available resources and accessible technologies in Europe was such luck! To have the possibility to go all the way from collecting planktonic cells in the ocean to high-end cutting-edge imaging technologies is a unique opportunity to better understand these ecologically-important cells!' (1). Adriano Barbosa Da Silva points to a roadblock in accessing research data from human participants, which CORBEL helped him to overcome, 'CORBEL support during my project was fundamental to address the legal requirements needed prior to data sharing. Without RI support it would have been particularly challenging to liaise with the matched biobanks and make sure that their data-sets could be used in my research' (1).

Overall, 96% of our users either fully (83%) or partly (13%) agree with the statement 'open access to research infrastructures greatly improves the research efficiency of European scientists' (Q.U25). 69% of the users report that without access to the services and technologies provided by the CORBEL service providers, they would not have been able to perform their experiments nor obtain their results from another source (Q.U16). The main reasons were the financial burden (50%) and the lack of knowledge about the existence of the support (27%) (Q.U17). The financial support to conduct the project was rated appropriate by 59% of the users, whereas 23% rated the support too low. The reimbursement process was rated good by 36% and very good by 41% of the users. Suggestions for improvement include a larger budget for consumables and instrument time, better communication tools and more straight forward options for booking travel (Q.U28).

The connections to highly skilled experts that the CORBEL Open Call facilitated resulted in the establishment of many collaborations lasting beyond the end of the CORBEL project. 59% of users state that they have benefitted either highly or very highly from CORBEL in terms of setting up collaborations (Q.U15, Q.U32). Examples include the project of Johan Decelle who is organizing a workshop entitled 'Sample Preparation and Multiscale Imaging of Plankton - From the environment to the subcellular level' (2) jointly with his EuBI ERIC and EMBRC-ERIC Service Providers after the end of CORBEL (Q.U32).

1.2 CORBEL Open Call User benefits - Publications

The vast majority of CORBEL Open Call projects is going to result in one or more scientific publications (82%) (Q.U21). Extrapolating, we expect approximately 40 peer reviewed publications by 2021. However, at present several Open Call projects have not completed their visits yet. In particular, a significant fraction (75%) of 2nd Open Call projects got interrupted by the Coronavirus pandemic. Depending on the ability to conclude these visits at a later point, the estimate of publications will have to be corrected up or down. Publications will appear with a delay due to the time required for manuscript preparation, peer review process and patent application, and also since the results generated in the CORBEL Open Call potentially have to be viewed in the context of a larger scientific question and might be embedded in a larger study (Q.U21). The outcome of several projects has been presented as talks and posters at conferences (Q.U21). The first peer reviewed publications are also available (3-8). Exemplary for the Open Call projects, one user emphasized the impact on her research that the interaction with the CORBEL Service Providers had, which resulted in the development of models for two relevant processes in neurodegeneration, namely ROS management and fission-fusion cycling in mitochondrial dysfunction. One research article has already been published jointly with Service Provider Hans Westerhoff (ISBE) (3). Two manuscripts are at present under revision (Q.U21). **In addition to the publications generated as a direct result of the CORBEL Open Call grants, 86% of users report that CORBEL access provision has generated results that will have a positive impact on future work.** Users have rated the impact is either good, 27% or very good, 59% (Q.U7). Users further report that access to RIs will contribute to securing fellowships/other funding (50% good, 32% very good) (Q.U8; Q.U22; Q.U10). One user concluded 'The CORBEL grant allowed us to gather vital data for future work, data that will contribute to manuscripts, and preliminary data that should be possible to turn into new grant applications.'(Q.U10).

1.3 CORBEL Open Call User benefits - Innovation

The scientific value of the CORBEL Open Call projects is not only reflected in publications but also in the innovation potential of the output (Q.U22). Results generated in the Open Call projects led to innovation in different areas. Working with LS RIs in the CORBEL Open Call led to the routine incorporation of the accessed RNA-Seq technology (BBMRI-ERIC/ISBE) into R&D operations of the company of an industry user. **At least one Open Call project is in the process of generating IP as compounds 'will likely be patented and transferred to pharma or used for start-up creation' (Q22).** New products in development further include analysis tools and diagnostic kits. The use of advanced technologies gave novel insight into biological functions. One user reported 'our project is a beautiful example that illustrates the power of the combination of FIB-SEM microscopy and image processing for the ultrastructural analysis in cell biology and its potential to unveil new cellular compartments or new functions of cellular organelles' (Q22). Another user sees the innovativeness 'with regard to imaging for the tissue of interest and with regard to biological insight in the tissue' (Q22). Innovation is also described in terms of the extent of the output generated. A user reports 'the large scale data acquired [...] opens new avenues of research for my lab' (Q22). Another user values the high-throughput nature of the RIs for his research, as 'it allows to increase the successful rate of drug discovery' (Q22). Systems Biology approaches within CORBEL have produced model predictions that can be utilized in personalized medicine. One example is a project, in which a user sees potential in the implementation of the models generated in the Open Call project to include the connection between mitochondrial dysfunction during redox stress and processes involved in neuroinflammation and metabolism. Results further translate to clinical applications in regards to redefined and more

accurate drug prescription, e.g. 'therapeutic response to certain inhibitors', and to drug development and 'translation to clinics' (Q22). In this regard, several oncology approaches were successful. Two projects focused on drug discovery against acute myeloid leukemia, two on cancer metastasis of colorectal cancer, one on breast cancer and one on melanoma.

2. Impact of integrated access standards on CORBEL Open Call Service Providers

The CORBEL Open Call brought together more than 20 facilities from 10 different research infrastructures across life science to join forces and combine technologies and scientific expertise to support advanced research projects. Together, more than 90 cutting-edge services and technologies were made available including access to advanced imaging technologies, high-throughput screening, systems biology, 3D modelling, data repositories and biobanks. The CORBEL Open Call therefore widened the knowledge of RI staff on technologies and services offered by partner RIs. The service providers recognize the added value of the interconnection between RIs, as 37% ranked it good and 18% very good (CORBEL Final Service Provider Survey, Q.SP4). **73% of the service providers report they were able to use the knowledge exchange to their benefit (Q.SP6).** Due to the increasing complexity and interdisciplinarity of life science research projects, the requirement for the combined use of high-end and cutting-edge technologies will also increase. Therefore bridging service offers also becomes more and more important. The effectiveness of having a centralized project coordination to facilitate the connection was rated 55% good and 18% very good (Q.SP3). Transitioning between services requires a high communication effort and forces the RI staff to step out of their routine, which is both challenging. 22% of the service providers had not worked with other RIs at all before (Q.SP1), but **75% state that service provision within the CORBEL framework has increased their interest in collaborating with other RIs (Q.SP10).**

2.1 CORBEL Open Call Service Provider benefits - Shaping service provision

All service providers agreed that offering 'open access to research infrastructures greatly improves the research efficiency of European scientists (Q.SP12). By providing these services also the RIs benefit in multiple ways such as the maturation of their own service offer, application of their technologies in new fields, training, networking and collaboration. The impact of offering access provision to the CORBEL users on their activity as service provider was rated good by 27% and very good by 18% and was surpassed by a medium score (37%), stressing that the full potential of service provision within the CORBEL Open Call project is only unraveled when the services are building upon each other across RIs. However, the advanced and diverse nature of the selected CORBEL Open Call projects was highly appreciated. **73% of service providers report that the Open Call projects pushed them to develop their service offer further, demonstrating that working on new challenges can drive systems to new frontiers (18% high benefit, 55% medium benefit) (Q.SP7).** In respect to training and personal development of RI staff, 64% acknowledge the added value (18% very high benefit) (Q.SP9). 82% of service providers report that they benefit from collaboration established due to the CORBEL Open Call, 27% of them rate the advantage of the collaboration very high. One Service Provider argued 'the strongest point of the Open Call is the outreach to potential users' (Q.SP15). The CORBEL Open Calls also presented an opportunity for increased visibility towards industry. Industry user Miguel Aso from Provital emphasized 'we are so excited with the results that we will probably use their services in the future. This LS RI initiative has been great to us, not only because of the funding, but also because it has helped me to show my colleagues what can be done with these technologies!' (9). One service provider would like to see the established connections go beyond the Open Calls 'at the moment the interaction between RIs is passive and motivated only through the

user needs. It would be interesting to actively promote interactions between RIs' (Q.SP11). Solidifying the interactions in between RIs by means of setting up bilateral collaboration agreements is indeed a central part of the long term sustainability plan.

2.2 Bilateral collaboration agreements to sustain frequently requested pipelines

Sustainability of the pipelines that were commonly requested by users is of particular importance, due to the value for the scientific user community. The CORBEL funding allowed to establish the pipelines, to test common applications processes and service provision and to channel users from one RI to the next. After completion of the CORBEL project and without further common funding for cross-RI user access, it will be in the hands of individual RIs to sustain these individual pipelines. WP4 has driven the set-up of bilateral collaboration agreements (CAs) between LS RIs, whose service portfolios appear to be strongly linked to each other. Defining common goals and united efforts to continue joined service provision via bilateral CAs can be an essential step in this direction. The first CAs have been signed between Euro-BioImaging ERIC and Instruct-ERIC, Euro-BioImaging ERIC and EU-OS ERIC, and EMBRC-ERIC and Euro-BioImaging ERIC. **Besides processes for common service provision, the CAs also include aspects such as staff exchange programs, joined outreach activities, and the identification of potential funding mechanisms for supporting user access.** More CAs are currently being negotiated (e.g. ELIXIR and Euro-BioImaging ERIC, EU-OS ERIC and Instruct-ERIC, EATRIS and EU-OS ERIC). For a detailed description see D4.4.

3. Impact of integrated access standards highlighted in success stories

To give a few examples of the diversity of projects that were realized within the CORBEL Open Call, the following Success Stories were selected, further demonstrating the extent of the reach and the relevance of the CORBEL support in the life science community.

Morphology and structure of chondrocytes and their association with mineralizing tissues in shark and ray cartilage, Mason Dean (EuBI ERIC/EMBRC-ERIC).

Cartilage performs vital functions in the skeletons of vertebrate animals, forming the embryonic scaffold for patterning adult bone, contour fillers in noses and ears, and bearing surfaces in joints. Critical to cartilage function are its embedded cells (chondrocytes), which secrete and maintain their surrounding matrix as a process of growth and response to the mechanical environment. Understanding the roles played by these cells is vital to unraveling how skeletons grow, repair and manage loads. The skeletons of sharks and rays are composed largely of a cartilage similar to ours, but unlike our skeletons, those of sharks/rays continue to grow and mineralize throughout life. As a result, Mason Dean, a group leader at the Max Planck Institute of Colloids & Interfaces in Potsdam, Germany, and Ph.D. student Júlia Chaumel use these animals as unique systems for studying cartilage biology. The primary goal of their CORBEL-funded project is to develop protocols for sample preparation and high-resolution imaging for cells and mineralizing tissue in shark and ray cartilage. In a 6-month longitudinal study, active mineralization zones in living animals were marked with fluorescent calcium dyes to observe skeletal growth, while novel approaches to animal collection, tissue clearing and labeling methods were also developed. Furthermore, to visualize resultant tissue growth, extensive testing and adaptation of imaging technology was performed, with focus on both linear (e.g. fluorescence) and non-linear microscopy techniques (e.g. second harmonic generation).

Establishing High-throughput Methods to Study 'Mini-guts', Jenny Ostrop (EU-OS ERIC/EuBI ERIC)

The human gastrointestinal tract is a highly sophisticated organ. The gut epithelium consists of several specialized cell types in a distinct spatial arrangement that enable efficient nutrient uptake and form a barrier against commensal bacteria and pathogens. CORBEL user Dr. Jenny Ostrop from the Centre of Molecular Inflammation Research at NTNU in Trondheim, is using organoids - 'mini-guts' that form characteristic crypts and villi - to study the intestinal epithelium. Her scientific interest lies in the differentiation of stem cells into the diverse epithelial cell lineages. 'We are trying to find the molecular 'switches' that determine which cell types develop from the stem cells and how the epithelium is composed', explains Jenny. The organoids are grown in a collagen matrix and their handling is challenging and time-consuming. Having heard about the CORBEL Open Call for research projects from colleagues, Jenny applied for access to the high-throughput screening facilities at EU-OPENSREEN. During her visit, Jenny was able to automate several working steps in her experimental pipeline, thereby accelerating the workflow. This allowed her to screen a library of compounds that might influence organoid development for their effect on cell differentiation and organoid composition. As the next step, based on the screening results, Jenny is planning to visit Euro-Biolmaging to quantify the three-dimensional morphology of the organoids following certain treatments, using advanced microscopy techniques and automated image analysis.

Screening for active compounds against acute myeloid leukemia, Maria Paola Martelli, (EU-OS ERIC/EuBI ERIC).

Prof. Maria Paola Martelli focuses her research on acute myeloid leukemia (AML) with the aim to translate her findings into novel diagnostic tools and therapies. AML affects the maturation of myeloid blood cells leading to accumulation of abnormal cells and ultimately to bone marrow failure. AML accounts for about 80% of acute leukemia in adults with a grim prognosis in particular for elderly patients, often leaving allogeneic stem cell therapy as the only treatment option. Prof. Martelli is primarily interested in a genetic alteration, present in about one-third of AML cases, which was discovered by Brunangelo Falini, when she was a researcher in his lab and has remained a central research interest throughout her career. This mutation alters the properties of a phosphoprotein, which in its mutant form accumulates in the cytoplasm. Prof. Martelli's CORBEL project aims to identify small molecule compounds, which attack either the mutated phosphoprotein or a key partner. To this end, the first set of experiments was carried out by Prof. Martelli's PhD student Roberta Ranieri at the EU-OPENSREEN Node. Access to EU-OPENSREEN allowed her to screen their libraries against AML cell lines, which she characterized in her lab. After screening is completed and hits are analysed, selected molecules will be further evaluated using advanced imaging technologies at the Euro-Biolmaging Node. This project will hopefully be a step towards novel therapy options for AML, which are desperately needed and will have a positive impact on human health.

A multidisciplinary approach against breast cancer, Alexey Koval (EU-OS ERIC/Instruct-ERIC)

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is a particularly aggressive form of breast cancer. Although only 15-20% of all cases belong to this molecular subtype, it accounts for about 50% of breast cancer related deaths. The current treatment plan is surgery, chemotherapy and radiation. A targeted therapy would greatly improve treatment options and enhance survival rates. CORBEL user Dr. Alexey Koval's goal is to find drug candidates which can be developed further into a targeted therapy. Alexey, a senior researcher from the Katanaev lab, identified a promising drug target, for which he wants to identify small molecules that act on this target protein. A drug discovery project requires multidisciplinary efforts. Alexey started the CORBEL project already with lead compounds in

the pipeline. He is now working together with EU-OPENSREEN and Instruct on searching for new active compounds as well as improving the chemical properties of existing ones until a promising drug candidate evolves. In EU-OPENSREEN's screening unit Alexey was able to significantly increase the portfolio of the potential drug candidates to about a dozen sub-micromolar novel and specific compounds. Meanwhile, the Instruct Node has carried out structural studies to analyze the interaction of novel candidates with the target. This process typically undergoes several rounds of optimization, for which specific expertise of the CORBEL facilities is extremely helpful to Alexey.

Cystic fibrosis: identification of potential drug targets with microscopy and computational methods, Margarida Amaral and Hugo Botelho (EuBI ERIC/ELIXIR/ISBE)

Cystic fibrosis (CF) patients suffer from recurrent lung infections and typically have a shortened life expectancy due to dysregulation of fluid transport into the lung. CF is caused by mutations in the CFTR gene, encoding an ion channel membrane protein. Prof. Margarida Amaral's research focuses on normal and mutant protein CFTR, namely on the most frequent mutation which prevents correct traffic of the channel to the plasma membrane. She and her team member Dr. Hugo Botelho have been working with Euro-BioImaging to gain access to the high-throughput microscopy facility to identify putative drug targets. She is further remotely accessing ISBE and ELIXIR Nodes. At the ISBE Node the identified screen hits are prioritized to build dynamical network models of the endoplasmic reticulum quality control, responsible for preventing the mutant protein from reaching the cell surface. Together with ELIXIR target prediction models are then applied to predict likely targets for novel compounds that have an effect on CF. The identification of novel compounds to treat CF has proven to be an ambitious goal, since the complexity of appropriate approaches is high. Their implementation in a large database, such as ChEMBL, and the use of the EMBL-EBI computational infrastructure, facilitated by CORBEL, can significantly contribute to the identification of novel drug candidates for CF. The group has plans to use EU-OPENSREEN facilities in the future for compound screens.

Revealing the morphological plasticity of a cell in planktonic symbioses, Johan Decelle (EuBI ERIC/EMBRC-ERIC).

Symbiotic interactions with microalgae are widespread among today's oceanic plankton and play a significant role in the functioning of marine ecosystems. However, their basic functioning and the subcellular mechanisms by which a cell can accommodate and engineer an intracellular microalgal cell remain unknown. Dr. Johan Decelle, a young group leader at the University of Grenoble Alpes, has focused on revealing these mechanisms in his research. The goal of his project is to unveil the structural architecture of the microalgal cell and its integration into a host cell using cutting-edge imaging technologies. Working with the EMBRC Node has allowed him to collect his study material despite being based away from the sea with his institute. This site offers a favorable oceanographic context for the presence of symbiotic plankton in near-shore waters, which facilitate experiments on live cells. At the Euro-BioImaging Node, he used the 3D imaging technique FIB-SEM (Focused Ion Beam scanning electron microscopy) to visualize subcellular modifications of the photosynthetic machinery and the microalgal cell at high imaging volume before and during symbiotic interaction. What started as a project selected via the CORBEL Open Call developed into a long-term collaboration. All partners agree that this project will improve our knowledge of the functioning of planktonic symbioses and bring new evolutionary insights into chloroplast acquisition in eukaryotes.

Integrating EU-wide cardiovascular research datasets, Adriano Barbosa da Silva (EATRIS/BBMRI-ERIC/EuBI ERIC)

Projects like the UK Biobank aim to improve the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of several diseases, by following the health status of 500,000 volunteer participants, and anonymously capturing changes that could give clues on alterations of health condition, lifestyle or environment that could be associated with the onset of diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Dr. Adriano Barbosa's CORBEL project aims to extend the impact of large population studies, such as the UK Biobank, by identifying and collecting additional European CVD datasets that could be analysed in parallel in order to validate insights observed in the UK Biobank on an independent dataset. In this respect it was of critical importance for him to gain access to European Research Infrastructures (RIs) that could help with this task. A bulk search conducted by BBMRI using their negotiator service towards the BBMRI catalogue of biobanks identified 465 matches. In parallel, EATRIS coordination and support office, through its proprietary database of capacity available within the RI partner institutions, identified five institutions. Further discussions between Adriano and principal investigators at the identified institutions enabled by EATRIS allowed it to scale down to two institutions with the datasets fully matching Adriano's CVD query: Fondazione Ri.MED (Italy) and St. Anne's University Hospital (Czech Republic). EATRIS helped to establish a Data Protection Agreement between Adriano's university and Ri.MED via engagement with the respective data protection officers. Additionally, EATRIS supported Adriano with setting up a Memorandum of Understanding between his university and the Czech hospital as a first step to establish the necessary framework to have their data used in the scope of the project. Through the Euro-BioImaging Node in Rotterdam, preliminary work was performed for the deployment of the XNAT.bmia.nl imaging archive key for the integration of imaging datasets. Further support will be provided for the extraction of imaging features from the medical imaging data sets allowing QMUL to apply machine learning methods to stratify cardiovascular patients based on machine learning.

4. Impact of integrated access standards on the visibility of RIs

As laid out in the sections above, with the CORBEL Open Calls, WP4 has facilitated access to the services and technologies of the LS RIs for the scientific user community by establishing a platform of shared services between the RIs. The CORBEL Open Calls have had a vast impact on the visibility of the RIs, collaboration among RIs and between RIs and users, training and the realization of cutting-edge research projects, to name a few. To underline the power and the importance of these kinds of interdisciplinary cross-RI services, a series of outreach material was produced in collaboration with WP2. The brochure "For the Advancement of Science - Working with European Research Infrastructures" is structured into three parts (1). The introduction provides background on and impact of the joint work of the LS RIs. In the second part Success Stories - including the ones mentioned above - are highlighted. In the final part the RIs which have participated in the Open Call and have already committed to continuing joint operations are featured. A series of animated videos is currently in development (9). The videos aim to explain the concept and the mission of LS RIs, the individual and collective service offers and give detailed examples of services and successful projects. The outreach material that was generated on the results of the activities of WP4, in particular the CORBEL Open Call, will contribute largely to attracting further users, increasing awareness, and demonstrating the need for further joint efforts building on established pipelines. The print and video material cannot replace the centralized project coordination. However, for as long as coordinated funding will not be available, it is supposed to aid in the introduction to RIs to guide the

viewer through the shared services and to encourage users and service providers to continue tackling highly innovative interdisciplinary projects involving multiple RIs. For a detailed description see D4.4.

Next steps

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, several user projects, in particular of the 2nd Open Call, will not be able to finish their experimental plans within the time frame of CORBEL. Possible solutions to continue the projects as soon as lab operations can be reactivated are currently being evaluated. This is one out of two final deliverables in WP4. The framework for launching transnational open user access via the common LS cluster web portal¹ and RI specific user community communication channels is described in D4.4 lays the ground for continued collaborative efforts to realize cross-RI user projects. With the submission of the final deliverables, the work for CORBEL will come to an end. However, many of the described activities will continue, either on bilateral grounds between LS RIs, maintaining the opportunities for cross-RI access via bilateral agreements and joint calls, or jointly in the cluster to explore opportunities for future cross-RI calls with funders and deepen the alignment to include the full project life cycle, including FAIR data and analysis via EOSC-Life.²

The presented feedback has been extremely positive, the presented results demonstrate the power of service provision across RIs and unravel the scientific and societal impact of the scientific outcome, altogether strongly emphasizing the crucial need to support user access across RIs.

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¹ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/>

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Abbreviations

- BBMRI-ERIC: Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
- BRFAA: Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens
- CA: Collaboration Agreement
- CORBEL: Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services
- CNRS: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
- CRG: Centre for Genomic Regulation
- CIRMMMP: Consorzio Interuniversitario Risonanze Magnetiche di Metallo Proteine
- CSIC: Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas
- DKFZ: Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum
- EMBL-EBI: European Molecular Biology Laboratory-European Bioinformatics Institute
- EMBL: European Molecular Biology Laboratory
- EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
- EuBI ERIC: Euro-Biolmaging ERIC
- EU-OS ERIC: EU-OPENSOURCE ERIC
- FVB: Forschungsverbund Berlin e.V.
- HMGU: Helmholtz Zentrum München für Gesundheit und Umwelt
- ICFO: Fundacio Institut de Ciencies Fotoniques
- ISBE: Infrastructure for Systems Biology in Europe
- LS RI: Life Science Research Infrastructure
- MDC: Max Delbrück Center for Molecular Medicine
- RI: Research Infrastructure
- UMCU: Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht
- VUA: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
- WP: Work Package
- SZN: Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn

Delivery and schedule

This deliverable is delayed:

No

Appendices

Appendix 1: CORBEL Final User Survey

Final CORBEL User Survey

CORBEL WP4

Q.U1 Did you have prior knowledge of RIs before the CORBEL Open Call?

- Yes, I have been a user of RIs before
- Yes, I was aware but discovered new services
- Yes, I was already quite familiar with these services
- No, I learned about RIs via the CORBEL Open Call

Q.U2 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the quality of the services provided individually?

Q.U3 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the effectiveness of the centralized support throughout your whole project?

Q.U4 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the added value of the interconnection between RIs as established in the CORBEL framework?

Q.U5 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to communication and collaboration between individual service providers along your project pipeline?

Q.U6 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the scientific impact on your the project, in which your CORBEL work is embedded

Q.U7 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the impact of the results obtained on your future work?

Q.U8 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to securing future fellowships/other funding?

Q.U9 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to overall rating for the CORBEL access provision?

Q.U10 Please provide a brief explanation for your rating

I had full support to the RIs that I needed to use.

Interactions through and with CORBEL were generally very well organized and eventually became a key for several of our projects.

I do not have clues about it. I suppose that it would be good

no data yet....none!

Better initial definition of the match between providers and users should be done. I think this might have been accomplished in the 2nd call.

Fantastic service providers and resources - the only challenge was perhaps bridging the RIs, getting everyone to meet and interact is difficult simply because of juggling so many schedules. The CORBEL grant allowed us to gather vital data for future work, data that will contribute to manuscripts, and preliminary data that should be possible to turn into new grant applications.

overall : very good access to facilities. good or medium benefit for the added value of two RIs

There is a high level of commitment to support students to meet the objectives proposed in their project

The Corbel grant provided me access with some very important technologies that I simply had no access to. Excellent opportunity for students too

In general the communication with the RIs has not been very fluent and that has caused delays in the project. I think the main reason for this difficulty has been that RIs did not know how to handle the terms of the collaboration; what was included in the service and what wasn't. Nevertheless my opinion is very positive because I have contacted very qualified and highly involved persons in the RIs I will certainly work in the future with thanks Corbel. it was the first call and it's normal that things have to roll on to see where the problems are.be clarified

High commitment of the RI researchers was very valuable for our project.

Clear protocol and communication between service providers was missing

Professional, convenient and easy

Q.U11 To what extent did you benefit from access via CORBEL in terms of instrument usage?

- no benefit
- medium benefit
- very high benefit
- low benefit
- high benefit
- not applicable

Q.U12 To what extent did you benefit from access via CORBEL in terms of data & analysis tools?

Q.U13 To what extent did you benefit from access via CORBEL in terms of user support?

Q.U14 To what extent did you benefit from access via CORBEL in terms of training?

Q.U15 To what extent did you benefit from access via CORBEL in terms of collaborations?

Q.U16 Without the access to the services and technologies provided by the CORBEL service providers, would you still have been able to perform your experiments/obtain your results from another source?

Q.U17 If no, please select

- Otherwise not eligible to apply for access to the infrastructure(s)
- Too difficult to obtain access by applying directly
- Unable to pay the user fee
- Unable to pay travel and accommodation costs
- No knowledge about the existence of this support

Q.U18 Has CORBEL access increased your interest in using RIs?

Q.U19 What other resources/facilities are not available to you, but would you be interested in accessing?

At the moment, I do not have any idea

Other types of NGS

proteomics, protein-protein interaction computational analysis, virtual screening

Imaging and image analysis techniques, particularly in modern high-resolution microscopy and tomography techniques

A technology to assess protein-compound interaction inside the cell

Lab based support

Q.U20 Which aspect of the services/access provision could be improved?

The possibility to use part of the economic support to buy some reagents and not only travel grant

Access to BSL2 facilities

We have obtained poor results with our first service provider (XXX) at the moment. Despite this, we gained some experience in the preparation and delivery of the samples. Perhaps a monitoring report every six months of the results that service providers and provide to the users and vice versa can help in the compromise, control, consuming time, quality of the work, dedication .

Molecular modelling

logistic support, feedback from previous users could be helpful

Perhaps ways of linking and communicating between RIs, but otherwise it worked relatively seamlessly.

An extension of the project deadline equaling the COVID lockdown period. More understanding between the user and RIs before the call deadline. A wider offer of RIs dealing with the same technique.

Lab based support

User should Contact appropriate SPs & discuss feasibility, time schedule and risks of the application before submitting Service Provider: Provide tech notes with feasible and impossible examples

Q.U21 Do you have/expect publications, including talks and poster presentations, where results obtained from CORBEL access are included?
Please comment and provide the DOI, if available.

Q.U21 Do you have/expect publications, including talks and poster presentations, where results obtained from CORBEL access are included? Please comment and provide the DOI, if available.

We expect to publish at least 2 papers in 2020 with the data obtained through RI interactions, and likely several more publications will result from screening results in future.

The interaction with ISBE-Amsterdam (Kolodkin/Westerhoff) is having a great impact on my research. They made two models that describe the properties of two relevant processes in neurodegeneration: ROS management and fission-fusion cycling in mitochondrial dysfunction. The main manuscripts that we have produced together with ISBE-Amsterdam (Kolodkin/Westerhoff) are both under revision. However, we have published the following article with Hans Westerhoff. Colangelo AM, Cirillo G, Alberghina L, Papa M, Westerhoff HV (2019). Neural plasticity and adult neurogenesis: the deep biology perspective. *Neural Regen Res.* 2019 Feb;14(2):201-205. doi: 10.4103/1673-5374.244775.

The following presentation included data from CORBEL access: ORAL COMUNICATIONS Levante A., Ferrari A., Yamaguchi Y., Montanini B., Chatzopolous D., Vatsellas G., Makrythanasis P., Neviani E., Folli C., Lazzi C. (2019) Toxin-antitoxin systems in bacteria isolated from food: a focus on genus *Lactobacillus*. SITOX Scientific Group on Natural Toxins, 2nd Meeting on "Natural toxins" 18-19/09/2019, Università degli Studi di Parma, Parma, Italy Levante A., Ferrari A., Yamaguchi Y., Montanini B., Chatzopolous D., Vatsellas G., Makrythanasis P., Neviani E., Folli C., Lazzi C. (2019) Toxin-antitoxin systems: a needle in the *Lactobacillus* genome haystack. 5th international conference on Microbial Diversity. 25-27/09/2019 Catania, Italy POSTER PRESENTATION Levante A., Ferrari A., Folli C., Thanos D., Makrythanasis P., Vatsellas G., Chatzopoulos D., Dionnelis V., Kawano M., Yamaguchi Y., Montanini B., Lazzi C., Neviani E. (2018) Toxin-antitoxin systems of *Lactobacillus casei* group: identification and transcriptional activation in response to food-related stress. *Food Micro* 2018. 3-6/9/2018, Berlin, Germany.

Q.U21 Continued

doi: 10.3390/v12010116

We have hopes to publish a paper in the future.

Communication at the next Congress of the Italian Society of Andrology and Sexual Medicine, October 2020

Technical poster on saliva RNA collection for NGS

not available yet

Upcoming, two papers and two talks are currently planned. Will provide information in the future.

The project supported by CORBEL was presented at the EMBO conference of image processing and analysis at the EMBL. The work will be potentially published in a peer-to-peer reviewed journal before the end of 2020.

We still have not prepared any of these publications, because it implies publishing proprietary data, but we will surely do once our ingredient is on the market.

I expect a manuscript published sometime 2020 that will acknowledge support from CORBEL, based on the analysis work. Â

We are preparing three articles: 1-Microplastics quantification with Raman Spectroscopic techniques (ICFO) 2.- Microplastics effects to Sea urchin larvae, adults and *Amphioxus* (SZN) 3.- Electronic microscopy for microplastics identification in marine sediments samples (only if St Andrews University collaboration is effective)

Q.U21 Continued

Three different studies from my project were being carried out in three RIs in Strasbourg, Berlin and Florence. The results were expected to be obtained in time but the COVID crisis has caused a suspension of all of them

I expect a publication coming from the living material harvested thanks to financial and logistic support by CORBEL

We presented one poster in an international meeting containing preliminary results obtained thanks to the collaboration with a Corbel RI .

DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2019.108948 DOI: 10.1016/j.toxlet.2018.06.1023

Talk 2019: CRC 854 retreat, Quedlinburg Poster 2020: International conference on learning and memory, Magdeburg

Q.U22 Do you see an innovation potential with the results you obtained in your CORBEL project?

Q.U22 Do you see an innovation potential with the results you obtained in your CORBEL project?

Yes, new products could be created via the usage of the infrastructures that we had access to.

Some of the compounds we have identified will likely be patented and transferred to pharma or used for start-up creation.

The possibility to implement the models in the future as to include the connection between mitochondrial dysfunction during redox stress and processes involved in neuroinflammation and metabolism. This would have a great innovation potential in terms of model predictions and their utility in terms of personalized medicine

CORBEL access allowed to expand knowledge on our research topic.

Our project is a beautiful example that illustrates the power of the combination of FIB-SEM microscopy and image processing for the ultrastructural analysis in cell biology and its potential to unveil new cellular compartments or new functions of cellular organelles.

More accurate drug prescription

Development of diagnostic kits.

drug development and translation to clinics

With regard to imaging for the tissue of interest and with regard to biological insight in the tissue.

From our company perspective, the RNA-Seq is a potent tool that we may perform routinely.

Q.U22 Continued

The large scale data I was able to acquire will be beneficial for my future funding scheme, and opens new avenues of research for my lab

We were going to get interesting data about the activity of novel compounds against a protein involved in cancer metastasis using two biophysical techniques from Strasbourg and Florence and another one cell culture-based. This screening would have allowed us select one drug to be tested in preclinical studies. We are doing that with one compound with excellent results but this compound was not obtain within the Corbel framework. The high-throughput nature of the RIs would allow us to increase the successful rate of drug discovery.

We hope to routinely use and implement the analysis tools generated by the Corbel RI team and take advantage of the knowledge we acquired from the RI researchers in our future research projects.

Q.U23 Would you recommend access to RIs as provided via CORBEL?

Q.U24 Please explain your choice to recommend or not to recommend

This is a unique opportunity to empower ones project with resources not available in house.

This way of accessing RI is very efficient and clear.

Of course, Yes, I would recommend, because I have been able to perform studies that I was not able to do on my own
no data

Despite the poor results that we have at the moment, I recommend the service that Corbel provide in different areas to other researchers

The support from the CORBEL was useful for partner identification and to initiate the dialog

Good coordination of the action

A fantastic way to make (and fund) unexpected ties to labs, learn new techniques, gather cutting edge data, and make new friends

Very helpful and competent

There are good professionals, technicians, work teams and scientific equipments that help carry out experiments with reliable results.

RIs included in the Corbel are supposed to be willing to cooperate with the users and that implies an important predisposition for establishing collaboration and making good research.

Yes. The expertise of the RI researchers was crucial to achieve our goal.

The possibility to use trans-national research infrastructures is an added value to fosters EU-wide collaborations and to get access to professionally managed core facilities with cutting edge equipment

Q.U25 Open access to research infrastructures greatly improves the research efficiency of European scientists.

Q.U26 Was the financial support appropriate?

Q.U27 How do you rate the reimbursement procedure for the costs associated with this project?

Q.U28 If you have suggestions for improvements, please let us know

no data...none!

The financial support although initially was low, was then upgraded as additional funding which was enough for the experiment be done.

It would be nice to be able to pay for some things directly (e.g. flights) to avoid having to be reimbursed each time, but that is just a minor gripe :)

Probably, it could be done more research if some money dedicated to visit could go to consumables. It depends on the RIs. Some of them really prefer to do the experiments by their own and not spending time of teaching the user. I perfectly understand that point.

To facilitate/improve the communication between the user and providers (visits, remote audiovisual exchange)

Running costs of expensive instruments might be a limiting factor for the number of experiments

Q.U29 How did you cover the costs of the consumables? If you used a grant, please let us know which grant it was.

Partly it was covered by CORBEL; otherwise by SNF and Innosuisse grants

I covered the cost of consumables with my own Italian funds for MIUR. But, they were not sufficient to buy consumables to run experiments at EMBL-ALMF.

CORBEL funding

this work was funded by two grants From Ministerio de EconomÃa y Competitividad from Spain AGL2014-56193-R and BFU2013-43149-R.

We covered all costs (sample preparation, Fedex). Corbel covered the costs for FIB-SEM imaging.

Corbel covered the costs of NGS consumables

Asked for additional funding from Corbel, which was granted, used seed money from the research unit for part of tge

ERCCo2016 n. 725725

An ASSEMBLE+ grant as well as some in-house money from my institute.

ATIP Avenir, HFSP CDA

From CORBEL itself.

own grant & other sources.

The consumables was covered by a local Project financed for Catalonia Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries Department (DARP) for microplastics studies in Tarragona coast

Q.U29 Continued

We paid the consumables expenses fro grants from the swiss national fundation

In certain occasion I used fund form a grant (PI/15 00626) from the Spanish Ministry of Health

Very few consumables were needed.

Public national grant.

Euromix project grant

CRC 854 TP Z01, research group budget

Q.U30 Are you aware of other funding mechanisms for transnational user access to RIs? If yes, please provide some information.

Q.U30 Are you aware of other funding mechanisms for transnational user access to RIs? If yes, please provide some information.

Besides ASSEMBLE+, no

LaserLAB EUROPE: I was supported by LaserLAB to perform experimental trials with optical tweezers at the University of Amsterdam in the Wuite lab.

And I would like to know more about these funding possibilities.

No, I am not but I would like to receive information about other funding mechanisms.

Q.U31 Having accessed services through the Open Call, would you be prepared to pay for similar services in the future?

Q.U32 Please provide an explanation for the choice above.

No, this fall beyond the grant available for projects on my institution.

We plan to continue collaboration with RI and will fund it through our own means.

I think that I would not be able to pay such services, because at the moment my economic resources are low.

Despite representing a great opportunity, might need to compare fees across other facilities.

no data...none!

Similar services are very expensive and/or they are not available in most of the research centers or countries . High quality personal and infrastructure is needed . Thus , it is a very good opportunity and solution for research apply to the Corbel Call in order to have access to important and sometimes unique services as the services that Corbel provides.

I would pay only if I had funding, but this is very difficult for us, a modest group. That's why we are so grateful to Corbel !

No persona funding

Only if there was a grant funding the project.

if not available as service in our laboratories

Depending on cost, yes - the expertise helped us troubleshoot in ways that would have been impossible at our home institute. Of course, we would also love to apply for other opportunities like CORBEL in the future :)

The service I obtained goes beyond the usage of a platform. I now established a permanent collaboration.

WE would lie to just repeat the same process with new ingredients.

I would be interested if provided to a fair price, but depending on the lab's future financial status.

Q.U32 Continued.

Yes, but we would need a support for financial resources through big projects with or not foreign partners

Again I don't have access to the infrastructure that was provided by the Corbel grant

That's a good point. I would pay for service that deserve it. Sometime is difficult to know which RIs would satisfy your research needs. Corbel is a good way to know that.

It's not easy to get grants to cover for those kind of services outside CORBELOpen Call

Yes, if we can afford it.

If service is not planned in a project, will be difficult to cover. However, service provider can be a project partner/service can be planned as external service provider.

The professional and user-friendly service accelerates finding research results and is worth to spend money from own annual budget or grants

Q.U33 Your opinion matters! Please type here any other comments or suggestions you might have.

I think we would profit of a central office booking the travel / accommodation for the RIs visits.

The possibility to use part of the economic support to buy some reagents and not only travel and accommodation grant

no data...none!

First of all, thanks to Corbel for this opportunity. I would like to comment that we were preparing some new samples in order to send to our first service provider (XXX) and improve our results, when the irregular situation caused by the SARS-CoV2 interrupted our plans. We would like to try again some experiments with our first service provider (XXX) and our second service provider (XXX), how would like to process our data, when we have acceptable results. Thus, hopefully we can re-start the activity after a normal situation come back to Europe with both service providers.

We are very thankful to Corbel for this unique opportunity !!

The people who supported our trips were fantastic: xxx and xxx in Banyuls, the whole ICFO team and especially xxx, who tolerated a ton of annoying questions from our side. THANKS!

Q.U33 Continued.

For me it was a rewarding experience, i would like a final meeting with the three institutions involved to discuss the analyzed results

The involvement of the RIs in the user's project is now equal. In rare occasions I had the feeling they were not interested in participating . This implication should be standardized somehow. All user should sign a form acknowledging that the research published within Corbel must include the RIs as co-authors. I never got to know the amount of money dedicated to the service. This information is important for the user to decide which experiments are feasible and which aren't. I will certainly extend the deadline of the project considering the COVID crisis to get the results the Corbel program needs for its evaluation as a scientific initiative.

Increase the duration of the program (at least 3 years) would be beneficial.

Appendix 2: CORBEL Final Service Provider Survey

Q.SP2 If yes, please specify in which context/project.

1.Hellenic Network of Precision Medicine in Oncology 2.Hellenic Network of Precision Medicine in Cardiology

PID6031, EMBL/DKFZ

iNEXT

We are part of LASERLAB Europe. Different user access our microscopy unit

Instruct, iNEXT

Health-RI / TraIT (dutch projects); FP7 BiomedBridges

ELIXIR/Euro-BioImaging - collaboration on image data management

Q.SP3 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the effectiveness of the centralized project coordination?

Q.SP4 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the added value of the interconnection between RIs?

Q.SP5 How do you rate the CORBEL access provision during this Open Call with respect to the impact on your activity as service provider?

Q.SP6 To what extent did you benefit from providing services in the framework of the CORBEL Open call with respect to knowledge about the service offers of other RIs?

Q.SP7 To what extent did you benefit from providing services in the framework of the CORBEL Open call with respect to the development of your service offer

Q.SP8 To what extent did you benefit from providing services in the framework of the CORBEL Open call with respect to collaborations?

Q.SP9 To what extent did you benefit from providing services in the framework of the CORBEL Open call with respect to training/personal development?

Q.SP10 Has the provision of services within the CORBEL framework increased your interest in collaborating with other RIs?

Q.SP11 Which aspect of the services/access provision could be improved?

The approval stage for projects appeared rushed and further safeguards could have been put in place should researchers not follow through

More detailed project applications in respect to experimental workflows

At the moment the interaction between RIs is passive and motivated only through the user needs. It would be interesting to actively promote interactions between RIs

More contact and update between the services and users

Documentation

Q.P12 Open access to research infrastructures greatly improves the research efficiency of European scientists.

- I fully agree to this statement
- I partly agree to this statement
- I am neutral
- I disagree with this statement
- I strongly disagree with this statement

Q.SP13 Without the support of this CORBEL Open Call would you still have been able to provide your services to CORBEL users?

- Yes, fully possible without the CORBEL resources (PM) as part of the regular activity of my RI
- Yes, but only partly without the CORBEL resources (PM) attributed to my RI
- Not sure it would have been possible without the CORBEL resources (PM) attributed to my RI
- No, this was possible only with the CORBEL resources (PM) attributed to my RI

Q.SP14 If no, please indicate the reason(s)

Most of services would not be possible

Extra functionality was implemented using the CORBEL support.

Q.SP15 Your opinion matters! Please type here any other comments or suggestions you might have.

This was a very good idea to bring RIs together in coordinated services! This efforts should continue!

Overall my group's involvement has been marked by the only RI participant that contacted myself. This RI participant never attend my institute and a lack of clear communication between the parties was a constant issue. It has left myself jaded at the process even though I believe the idea behind open calls like CORBEL is essential and I fully support. As an aside CORBEL's focus seemed to change to further embrace imaging as the primary RI being disseminated. It's also an area where RIs like this can make huge impact. However my group does not work on imaging and therefore the focus of the calls seemed more distant to our day to day activities than before.

The review process for project applications was based on technical feasibility and not on detailed experimental conditions resulting in meaningless cost calculations as some projects planned for 5 parallel sub-projects without notification and were surprised about 5fold amount of costs not covered by initial estimated budgets.

CORBEL is a quite ambitious project. The number of RI was high. This were also highly diverse. This may benefit some users. To strengthen EU collaborations, a more contained set of RI, working around a small collection of "TRACKS" would have, in our view, concentrated a larger number of users and more successful collaborators.

I think that the aim of CORBEL to serve the European life science community by creating faster, easier and more efficient open access to European research infrastructures through the establishment of common service pipelines is great idea but not easy to coordinate and need more update between users, services and corbel

Q.SP15 Continued

We are very happy for the financial support for our visitors and the facility staff. In addition, we are able to test different workflows with one of our CORBEL visitors, which will help us in testing running conditions for a new microscope that we have acquired. CORBEL has really helped in financially supporting a workshop to be held in France in May bridging cell biologists and marine biologists.

The strongest point of the Open Call is the outreach to potential users. By grouping different related services in access tracks, researchers are guided through the maze of different services offered by different infrastructures providers.
